

OPTIMUM DESCRIPTION OF YARN AXIS GEOMETRY IN WOVEN COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Quantitative composite structure description is an important task from both the theoretical and practical point of view. Among all in principle applicable methods for yarn axis description or approximation the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) appears as the best suitable one, since it respects yarn periodicity or quasi-periodicity and its output, the spectrum, has a simple and straightforward physical meaning. It can be applied at least in two ways for quasi-periodic function and general closed curve description. On the other hand, the DFT should be used carefully; otherwise unwanted effects appear, such as spectrum leakage that complicates simple and efficient use of outputs. This effect takes a place, when non integer number of periods is sampled. Main application of DFT are presented in the paper: efficient yarn axis approximation, spectrum filtering for removing of experimental errors (like sample bending), effective approximation of general form of closed curve that is a contour of void cuts in composite structure. Also method for leakage reduction is shown. Practical results are mainly in graphical form.

KEYWORDS: Textile composite, Woven reinforcement composite, Composite structure, Image analysis and processing, Yarn axis geometry, Discrete Fourier Transform, DFT

INTRODUCTION

Woven reinforcement composites are used in many industrial areas thanks to some their excellent properties that are determined mainly by their specific materials and structure. Due to the technological processing, composite exhibits a more complicated structure than incoming free woven fabrics. Furthermore, the structure of free woven fabrics differs from ideal one used in models. Especially yarn axis geometry changes strongly during composite production process. Its suitable and reliable approximation is necessary, from many reasons: better understanding the composite technology, control and improvement of composite production, input for Finite Element Method (FEM) to predict real material properties, source for determination of statistical parameters of product selected properties, etc.

Probably, the yarn longitudinal axis shape brings the most important information on composite real structure. However, full description of the composite structure needs knowledge of yarn cross section shape as well. The structure does not contain only the yarn and matrix (resin). There are a lot of imperfections; the most important of them are voids. They should be also included into complete structure description as well as yarns. Also a representative volume of real sample must be selected to make reliable statistics.

Mathematical description or approximation of yarn longitudinal axis is a subject of research interest for a period of almost one hundred years. The purpose of this paper is not to get a complete overview of all approaches; it can be found in specialised monographs. We only state that the description become more and more exact thanks to the rapid increase of very efficient computational methods and equipments. In the last two decades the massive use of

personal computers allowed to use methods and perform calculations that were impossible by simple means.

The real yarn axis is too complicated to be described exactly. However, the efficient approximation including all its basic features is possible thanks to modern computer assisted methods. They allow many approaches; the well-known ones are these:

1. Least square method for polynomial approximation
2. Application of splines
3. Approximation by a selected function using non-linear fitting
4. Application of Fourier series or specialised Fourier transform
5. Method of wavelets

Efficient application of these methods has strict limitations. Very important feature, the yarn quasi-periodicity, shows that the least square method is a least suitable one. If we require not only geometric approximation, but also the use of its parameters for further study, the splines should be omitted, since their parameters have no simple and evident geometric or physical meaning. If we seek for uniqueness and reliability, the nonlinear fitting is not a good approach, since it may give little different results or it may not converge at all. The wavelets are very efficient new method, but its understanding and application is complicated and, may be, the results are difficult to be interpreted simply.

From this short discussion the Fourier transform appears to be ideal for longitudinal yarn axis approximation. It deals with periodic or quasi-periodic functions, all the computed parameters have simple and straightforward interpretation, the application is robust and unique, and the user can select the degree or quality of approximation. Since the experimental data from real yarns are in a digital form, the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) should be used. Its use is very simple, but there is little danger of its improper application.

Furthermore, the DFT is not limited to the yarn longitudinal axis approximation. It can be used for the approximation of any structure object of general cross sectional shape as well. In the case of yarn the approximation of its cross section by ellipse or by lenses is usually acceptable; however, the application of DFT method is probably the only one approach for approximation of the cross section of a void. In this paper the application of DFT for the effective description of structure objects is presented. Special processing of DFT outputs can lead to surprising effects that are mentioned. In the paper the emphasis is focused to the proper use and demonstration of DFT possibilities.

EXPERIMENT

In the experiment the carbon-carbon composite was used. The optical microscopy was used for scanning the composite sample cuts obtained by standard metallographic technique. Irrespective of many disadvantages of optical microscopy, the perspective Computer Tomography (CT), see for instance Ref. 1, cannot be used, because of its low resolution either in high quality laboratory equipment.

The detailed actual yarn centre line geometry was derived from very high resolution optical microphotographs of composite structure. Part of the typical structure is shown in Fig. 1. In Fig 1a there are marked longitudinal yarn edges and in Fig. 1b the marked contour of a void is shown. It is clear from this representative photograph that yarn shape differs from the ideal course considerably. Also the void dimensions in Fig. 1b are comparable with yarn cross section dimensions.

The structure evaluation needs to find object boundaries. Especially in the case of yarns, the contrast between yarn and its environment is low, therefore neither modern sophisticated methods of image analysis are able to make correct yarn boundaries automatically. The best approach is to mark the edges manually by an experienced operator. If different colors are used systematically, many yarns can be marked and exactly identified. Enhanced yarn edges marked by white color are visible in Fig. 1a. Any other image processing is made automatically by computer program. In our case the coordinate of longitudinal yarn axis were computed and saved in a text file. Therefore, the finest yarn axis sampling is in pixels. The sample coordinates are input for DFT.

Fig. 1: Structure microphotographs and their object hand processing: a) yarns, b) voids

The procedure described above results in yarns axis given by points. Two typical examples of yarn axes in C/C composite consisting of 8 layers are in Fig. 2. About three times higher pressure was used for sample in Fig. 2b. The yarn axis shape is far from ideal one, nevertheless, it exhibits quasi-periodicity.

Fig. 2: Yarn axes in composite: a) low pressure, b) high pressure

The second application was to find the contour of void cuts. Demonstrating results are in Fig. 3. Approximately central part of void is in Fig. 3a and the profile for cut near void top its in Fig. 3b. The scales in both the parts of Fig. 3 are different. It is clear from this illustration that the void exhibits complicated shape, especially in its central part.

THEORY

It is well-known from circuit theory that the signal can be described in the time or frequency domain. The descriptions are equivalent, no old information is lost and no new information appears. The key feature that leads to frequent use of both the domains is the fact that some

feature in one domain has very simple understanding form, while in the second domain the same feature not practically visible. The transition between two domains is made in general by the Fourier transform. Strictly speaking, in the case of composites the yarn axis forms a signal in the coordinate domain and the second domain should be the wave-number domain. For simplicity and to be compatible with signal the time and frequency domain will be used frequently.

Fig. 3: Void profiles: a) central part, b) near top

In time domain the information is usually in a graphical form, in frequency domain it is in a form of spectrum (discrete, continuous, or digital depending on the type of function in time domain). The physical meaning of spectrum is simple and straightforward. Each spectral line in frequency domain corresponds to the harmonic waveform in time domain. The spectral line has two components: amplitude and phase shift. The amplitude in spectrum is the amplitude of harmonic waveform, while the phase shift determines its position to the origin of time axis. It can be the position of its first zero for positive time given in radians, for instance. In the case of Fourier series and DFT the functions are termed harmonics.

Physical meaning of (amplitude and phase) spectrum is straightforward. The original function in time domain is a superposition of harmonic functions that are given by all spectral lines (discrete or continuous) in frequency domain. The harmonic functions of determined amplitudes are added with a given phase shift. The phase shifts have usually much strong effect into the resulting waveform than the amplitudes. As it has been already said, by performing the Fourier transform, no information is lost and no added. However, the information contained in spectrum is in quite different form, it has many new features and can be very efficiently processed.

The formula for direct and inverse formulae for DFT are usually written in the form

$$\hat{X}_n = \sum_{p=0}^{N-1} u_p e^{j\frac{2\pi}{N}pn} \quad (1)$$

$$u_p = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \hat{X}_n e^{-j\frac{2\pi}{N}pn} \quad (2)$$

where u_0, u_1, u_{N-1} are yarn axis coordinates (in time domain) and \hat{X}_n are complex amplitudes of spectral lines (frequency domain). The physical meaning of complex amplitude \hat{X}_n is that the module $|\hat{X}_n|$ is the amplitude and phase angle φ_n is the phase shift. Amplitudes form

amplitude spectrum and phase shifts contributes to phase spectrum. Both the spectra are of the same importance and fully describe the yarn axis in frequency domain. Usually, only the amplitude spectrum is displayed because of its simple understanding. For completeness, if the number of samples N is a power of 2, a very fast calculation of DFT is possible; the algorithm is termed the Fast Fourier Transform, FFT.

A care must be taken when the DFT is used. The experimental function is digitalized and the digitalization results in the set of equidistant samples. The DFT applied to the samples produces a set of equidistant spectral lines or harmonics as output. The number of complex harmonics equals to number of samples. DFT can be applied only to function of finite length. However, the DFT formula is defined on the whole time or frequency axis. The application of DTF formula outside the basic function or spectrum interval results in infinite periodic replication of both the original finite length function and basic spectrum. Therefore, no new information is present outside given intervals in both the time and frequency domain.

A care must be taken if the function is periodic or quasi-periodic. In this case the DFT use can lead to erroneous results that appear as two effects:

1. aliasing
2. leakage

Aliasing leads to false spectral lines as a consequence of sampling less than 2 times per period. In the case of textile yarns, the sampling is fine; aliasing does not take a place.

Leakage is a consequence of spatial and frequency periodicity. The optimum sampling is to sample integer number of periods. In this case the spectrum has the simplest possible form and the replicate signal in time domain is perfectly periodic. If this condition is not valid, the spectrum contains more harmonics and they have higher amplitude. The term leakage follows just from the growing of spectral lines. In time domain the signal periodicity is corrupted at the contact of neighboring replicas. It means that output of inverse DFT is not exactly the original signal.

APPLICATION

Two quite different areas of DFT application suitable for composite structure study will be presented in this chapter:

1. Longitudinal yarn axis processing
2. General closed curve description

Longitudinal Yarn Axis Processing

The typical result of DFT is the spectrum that consists of two parts of the same importance: amplitude and phase spectrum. Both the spectra for almost ideal sampling with suppressed leakage are shown in Fig. 4. The ideal sampling was achieved by removing a suitable number of samples from starting or finishing part. Parts or amplitudes of amplitude spectrum, like that in Fig. 4a, have simple interpretation: the maximum 6th harmonics means that about six periods is in time domain. Relatively small neighbors of this harmonics deduce its low distortion; it will be similar to pure harmonics (sine or cosine). High values of low harmonics (1st, 2nd, 3rd) are result of the yarn overall distortion, in this case the yarn bend as a whole. The yarn axis is not positioned symmetrically with respect the horizontal line. Small high harmonics confirm low noise. The inspection of Fig. 8c bellow confirms the predictions. Unfortunately, the phase spectrum, irrespective of its importance, has no such simple explanation.

The frequency domain allows important practical operations. Since most of harmonics are very small, yarn axis can be well approximated by several, the most important, spectral lines. The number of approximating harmonics depends on function complexity and quality of approximation. For instance, six the most important harmonics of spectrum in Fig. 4 are probably enough for a satisfactory approximation of the yarn shape in time domain, see Fig. 7 below.

Fig. 4: Frequency domain-spectrum: a) amplitude, b) phase

Other interesting DFT application is filtering in frequency domain. In the simplest case the filtering removes selected spectral lines. As a consequence of spectrum change, the yarn axis is modified. Therefore, a systematic filtering could lead to improvement of yarn axis, for instance, by reducing some experimental errors. On the other hand, yarn axis approximation by the most important harmonics is an example of very special and complicated filtering.

General Closed Curve Description

Other very important application is the use of DFT for closed curve approximation. Simple closed curves as circle or ellipse can be presented as a trajectory of a point that makes two perpendicular harmonic vibrations of the same frequency. The phase shift affects the ellipse shape. If the frequencies are not the same Lissajouse figures appear. Therefore, arbitrary closed curve can be considered as a superposition of suitable Lissajouse figures. The idea of use DFT for closed curve approximation is similar. Both the x and y coordinates are considered as functions of a parameter, for DFT the parameter is an index of the coordinates. Both the coordinate sets are processed by DFT and then approximated by several most important harmonics. An example of such approximation is in Fig. 5.

The second step is the calculation of approximated coordinates from selected harmonics. Then approximated curve is composed from them. A result for approximated coordinates from Fig. 5 is shown in Fig. 6. Only y coordinate approximation is used in Fig. 6a, while both coordinates are approximated in Fig. 6b. Only three harmonics are used for approximation in order to see difference. If 6 harmonics are used the agreement is almost perfect. Because of rapid changes, the x coordinate approximation is difficult, see Fig. 5a. It results in surprising conclusion that no x coordinate approximation gives better results. However if the curve approximation is required, both coordinates must be approximated.

Fig. 5: Approximation of closed curve coordinates: a) x coordinate, b) y coordinate

Fig. 6: Approximation of closed curve: a) only y coordinate is approximated, b) both coordinate are approximated

RESULTS

Original menu driven SW written in C++ was developed for a wide application of DFT. It works both with analytical functions and experimental points, displays both the amplitude and phase spectrum, allows function approximation, spectrum filtering, special data processing, etc. Typical examples of the SW application will be presented in this section.

Very important task is the approximation of the yarn axis by the most important harmonics. An example of approximation by 5 harmonics is in Fig. 7. The quality of approximation depends on quality of sampling. If leakage is suppressed by proper sampling, the spectrum is very simple and the agreement with experiment is good in the all the parts of yarn axis, see Fig. 7a. However, in the case of incorrect sampling the spectrum is complicated and the approximation is not good at starting and finishing parts, Fig. 7b.

Another useful operation in frequency domain is filtering, i.e. changing amplitudes of suitable harmonics, in the simplest case removing group of hem. The simplest filters are low-pass, high-pass and band-pass; they remove high frequency harmonics, low frequency harmonics and both of them, respectively. The low pass filter, in general, removes experimental noise

and improves the quality of experiment data. Its effect is not important in the case of high resolution experiments as ours. The high-pass filter removes low harmonics.

As it was explained for amplitude spectrum above, low harmonics are due to the textile layer bending in the composite preparation. The bending differs from layer to layer; it does not have any practical information and should be removed by a suitable high-pass filter. The example of bending reduction is in Fig. 8. Harmonics from the 1st to the 4th were removed and the proper sampling length was used. In Fig. 8a the original and in Fig. 8b high-pass filtered spectrums are shown. In the lower part of Fig. 8, the original yarn axis, Fig. 8c, and the yarn axis after filtration, Fig. 8d, demonstrate the high-pass filter effect. The yarn bending is reduced, therefore graph after filtering contains information relating to the yarn itself and not to random production error.

Fig. 7: Approximation of yarn axis: a) leakage suppressed, b) leakage in effect

Fig. 8.: High-pass filter application: a) original spectrum, b) filtered spectrum, c) original yarn axis, d) yarn axis after filtration

Another application is the description of yarn cross section shape. In principle, the DFT can be used for general or elliptic approximation. However in this case the better agreement can be got by application of least squares for ellipse and nonlinear programming for two lens approximation [2]. In the case of lens approximation the procedure *fminsearch* in MATLAB is used to find optimum coefficients for circle arc (center position and diameter). The optimum is again the minimum of squares of deviations.

More important is the use of general closed curve approximation that is a contour of void, like those in Fig. 3. In this case the approximation of both coordinates by harmonics is probably the only possible solution. By making parallel cuts, the 3D void shape can be reconstructed. In Fig 9a there are curves for several parallel cuts. They correspond to level lines of earth surface in the map. But earth level lines do not cross. If the curves in neighboring parallel planes are connected by small triangles, the void surface can be modeled. An example of such surface between two adjacent curves is in Fig. 9b. If the triangle coordinates and face normals are found, the void 3D surface can be visualized very realistically by the use of virtual reality or Open GL system.

Fig. 9.: Void modeling: a) void map, b) surface of one void layer

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Probably, the DFT is the most efficient and flexible tool for yarn axis modeling, if it is used exactly. The paper has shown how to deal the spectrum leakage that can be the result of incorrect DFT application. If leakage is reduced, the user can get correct results suitable for evaluation of textile yarns and components from them. Other very efficient spectrum application helps to yarn axis approximation by a small number of well defined physical parameters, or removing un-important information.

The realized SW allows applying all of the above operations, but it is not limited to them. The SW exhibits many other useful features. Its main advantage is the correct (after proper set up of parameters) and automated data processing. In the future this SW can be used for statistic processing of yarns. The main expected result of this operation is to get both the systematic and random component of structure for a more complex yarn or composite evaluation.

Thanks to realised SW that makes easy use of DFT, this operation becomes very efficient tool for likelihood approximation of yarn axis geometry not only in real structures. The approximation is robust, all the approximating coefficients have obvious physical meaning, the quality of approximation can be selected, and the number of parameters is low, from 5 to 15 harmonics usually. The quality of approximation depends strongly on the yarn length. In general, the spectrum has the simplest form, if the origin function contains integer number of periods. In this case the approximation is also the best one. The SW allows cutting the origin function in order to meet this condition. Other very efficient SW application is filtering that can improve the original function. One of the simplest cases of filtering was demonstrated above.

Another very important application is the approximation of very general closed curves. They are typical for contours in cuts of voids. By the use of DFT they can be approximated very efficiently by a small number of parameters. Their use is for void modelling by 3D visualisation systems as Open GL, virtual reality and others.

The application of DFT is a very efficient tool in the study of real composite structure. Our method and results are probably original [3] and their wide use can be expected.

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